

The supply of intercultural communication

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Anotation:

In this article, education and production of intercultural relations pedagogical possibilities of influence on the process of social progress do it with cultural and educational factors that allow implementation the designation is given by.

Key words:

education, culture, interculturalism, multiculturalism, cultural pluralism.

“Intercultural communication” for the first time in 1954 and Trager G. E. hall's concept of “culture and communication. The analysis model” was introduced into scientific circulation in the works called. In this game “intercultural communication” in the way of man's own desire to strive to be ideal purpose the outside world is arguably a better and more effective it was interpreted as adaptation to the surrounding. Also, the game has developed new methods of studying culture and communication. Hence in the direction intercultural communication has formed currently by researchers to develop the theoretical aspects and he is enough.

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Available in our country many people respect the traditions and concepts that are relevant to them, to be in a good relationship as a cultural, as well as cultural heritage under the feet of every one to avoiding and our obligation to deliver the next generation. Another important aspect to achieve perfection in all areas of higher education institutions located all personnel, professional knowledge and purpose. Exactly what knowledge and skills, was able to answer all of the criteria foreign to modern language acquisition. In particular, Social solidarity-more than 130 nations and nationalities residing in to our constitution the principle of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov of Uzbekistan in the way of new building of their nationality, language, religion, sex, social origin and position in society look, and serves the further development of mutual cooperation. Thus, communication in relationships intercultural allows you to participate at all levels. In a time of rapidly developing information technology in the XXI century, the people of culture in the merger with the times together is going on, it won't be exaggeration if I say.

Intercultural industrialized countries in Europe that started the development of education after the second world war by the institute is the result of the pressure to make the refugee wave. In 60-70 years was the rapid development because of the presence of migrant in western European countries. Today, diversity issues in education policy and practice are included. In any matter, or managers, or professionals, or politicians, or members of international organizations, or between the common people social, economic, political, management, communication is necessary. Communication individuals, groups, or ethnic communities, human, history and various cultural roots occur between when we to deal with the communication between cultures. Cultures of all the relations between economic, social, political, organizational, in various countries, including institutions, agencies, businesses, organizations and agreements between human communities, established on the basis of bilateral or multilateral agreements on cultural communication. In Europe and outside the

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united states and Canada, the world at any point stress the importance of professional mobility of labor, to increase the percentage of those who are able to travel around the world another example of the relations between the cultures of mutual knowledge of the culture and civilization of other people and etc.

Life style life because it is useful to make contact with other members of direct changes in the various spheres of knowledge and will enhance means to travel, but most importantly, other people, life, culture and lifestyle and gives you information about who is real pleasing to believe(or electronic) that make up the library.

Intercultural communication - communication is designed for information sharing between different cultures and social groups this form. This term different religious, social, ethnic and education groups arising naturally from the person belonging to the organization founded in communicative processes and is used to describe a wide range of problems. Intercultural between culture and education is the result of education. The first type of Intercultural surveys in education - this is in the context of culture and the school transferred to the effects of minority status and associated with the role. Learning in two important respects cultural anthropology in the context of the subject of the class: micro macroethnographic and ethnography. Micro-ethnography studies reader / student, teacher / student relations are focused on issues such as the role of teaching and teacher.

Intercultural initial communication requires patience and time. Cultural comparison which is in contact with a foreign culture, education Intercultural, this is a key sign of any training program. On the basis of news value based on the network cross-cultural competence intersemiotic exercise form will require the development of translation and interpretation. Contact with other cultures and experience another culture news created by people who are in between the old culture is accomplished by simbioz. All available cultural eyes of the scheme and

